

INTERNET MEDIA

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Emerging media technologies including the Internet, print, broadcast, telecommunications, and computer communication have grown exponentially, creating new domains and leading to a convergence of media in general and global consumption of goods and services in particular. The new media are technologically driven channels of communication that facilitate "user-to-user" participation in the modern society. A 'many-to-many' web of communication emerged as a potential replacement for the traditional 'one-to-many' paradigm of mass communication with the introduction of the Internet. Currently, the internet is also one of the most significant tools for interactive communication. Interactivity has become a buzzword for a variety of new media use possibilities that have emerged as a result of the rapid spread of Internet access points, media digitization, and media convergence. In today's society, the internet has also become a significant communication channel.

The Internet is a vast network of communication networks that has altered the way people live, learn, work, earn, and communicate around the world. The Internet, commonly referred to as the 'NET,' is a network of computer databases and information services. The Internet is also referred to as the world without borders—neither in terms of time, location, or language. Its global reach and ability to link to any sort of computer have shattered communication barriers.

When the World Wide Web was launched, rapidly it became very popular, and then, in 1994-1995, some media companies all over the world began considering going through that service, and began to abandon Servicom or CompuServe. Some newspapers are considered to be the pioneers of Web journalism: in the United States, Chicago Tribune was distributed by America OnLine (AOL) since May 1992, and then,

in 1993, San José Mercury Center, Nando.net (an online version of the community local daily newspaper Nando Times) decided to go online, The Boston Globe decided some time later to create a community board and in Europe, one of the first was The Electronic Telegraph, an online version of The Telegraph. ¹

Wikipedia is an online popular encyclopaedia that defines what the Internet is and what it means: "The Internet is a worldwide, publicly accessible network of interconnected computer networks that use packet switching and the Internet Protocol to convey data" (IP). It is a "network of networks" made up of millions of smaller domestic, academic, business, and government networks that together transmit diverse information and services like electronic mail, online chat, file transfer, and the interconnected web pages and other resources of the World Wide Web (WWW). ²

The amount of time spent online is rising. The public has access to a vast amount of thorough information thanks to the internet. The newest thing in schooling is the internet. Internet and computer use are necessities for academic life. Students use the Internet to research topics in greater detail. It is a crucial resource for both the general public and academics. To best serve students, Internet usage might be simplified. The combination of computer and communication technologies forms the foundation of the Internet. Since the 1970s, both of these technologies have developed at a never-before-seen pace.

Online infographics were also common at that time. Online staffs grew up as well, and media webs were converted into portal, following a model began by Yahoo!, Netscape, America On Line (AOL) and Lycos. This was especially clear in Brazil, where Globo Group, one of the largest media-companies in Latin America (and all over the world) controls a majority of media in this huge country and determines the shape of many media-based websites (Herscovitz, 2009). In Europe, such model was not totally successful. One example is Le Monde which, through its trademark Le Monde

¹ Javier Díaz Noci. "A history of journalism on the internet: A state of the art and some methodological trends". Revista internacional de Historia de la Comunicación, Nº1, Vol.1, año 2013, PP. 253-272

² Abhram, William. "The Internet as a Modern-day Communication Medium." J Mass Communicat Journalism 12 (2022): 453.

Interactif, decided to launch a portal called tout.lemonde.fr in the Spring of 2000, and abandoned it in June of the same year.

New Internet technologies and mobility are producing a new type of “social product” connected to the architecture of these technologies. The individualization of consumption is growing at the expense of the “narrow attraction of active groups”. Imaginaire relationnelle (relationship virtuality) is being established as an oppositional practice of using the computer as a “rational reality.” Forms of entertainment are becoming more complex and are virtualizing, actively founded on play and scene-making as a way of life (exchange of fantasies, the building of a “spectacle” around oneself [mise en scène de soi], play with identity)³.

Multimedia, crossmedia, transmedia – these new characteristics of the nature of media, are fundamental. Multimedia leads to an instrumental universality of platforms which become crossmedia, and inherently production is the “subject,” and not the type of media. Transmedia and convergence become a philosophy of content, platforms, new professions and modern consumers of media. The role of journalists is changing. They no longer only record, obtain, film, write. They chose, verify (or don’t verify!), they “package” the information of eyewitnesses, who are armed with mobile telephones, keeping blogs, sending SMS texts, and exchanging information on social networks. Editorial boards are “directing” information streams; media business divisions are involved in cross-marketing. The nature of multimedia influences the competitiveness of mass media, and changes the strategy of traditional media and their online versions as the marketing tool develops the concepts of “augmented reality” and “second life” (a means of virtual existence as a person and as media)⁴.

A first step has to be made in terms of the developments on the technological front and the ways in which these developments are making inroads into our understanding

³ Anna Kachkaeva. “Digital media and the Internet market: Audiences, multimedia content and business models”. From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012 <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/8/3/102312>

⁴ Anna Kachkaeva. “Digital media and the Internet market: Audiences, multimedia content and business models”. From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012 <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/8/3/102312>

of journalism. Computerization in all sectors of society has taken place in particularly Western capitalist democracies - with effects on the way the economy and society operates. Practically all media companies have switched to computer network systems, electronic communication traffic and the 'paperless office' are topics of debate in management circles and the convergence of media as well as the fact that the television set, video player and personal computer have found their way into an increasing number of West-European, North-American and Australasian households are signs of the high impact of technology on all aspects of life. The Internet as it can be considered to be affecting journalism in general and the professional ideology of journalism in particular will be discussed here in two ways: how it has made inroads into newsrooms and desktops of journalists working for all media types in terms of Computer-Assisted Reporting (CAR); and how it has created a new type of journalism: online journalism. Although it must be said that every country or region has its own specific issues regarding new media developments and journalism, the author assumes that some of the more general points made here can be extrapolated to the developments in more or less similar areas in the world such as North America, Australia, Western Europe and Japan.⁵

There are some unique features that set the Internet apart. The Internet is, first and foremost, a live, interactive media platform. In other words, the Internet is a two-way channel for communication. A person who utilises the Internet is called a user, not a viewer or listener. "User" suggests being in charge and proactive. Users of the internet have two options for finding information: they either actively seek for it online or create their own content. Individuals evaluate the offered content and share their thoughts so that others can see them. Another facet of the Internet's interactivity is user interaction. Opinions and points of view are freely shared online.

The most important trend in the development of the new media is the speed and presence of millions of non-professionals who compete with professionals in

⁵ Mark Deuze. "Understanding the impact of the Internet: On new media professionalism, mindsets and buzzwords" (January, 2001). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254750080>

producing content. For Russia media, awareness of the final lost battle for speed of information with the networks came after the tragic terrorist act at the Domodedovo Airport (social network users overtook all media, and the media widely incorporated the content of eyewitnesses). Any modern editorial board is hard to imagine today without active promotion in social networks, without special columns (variations of diverse mobile reporters), incentivizing (for fame or for money) the former consumers of information to become its producers. Social media, more than traditional media, is oriented to discussion and creation of new values. This natural feature of social media is being used by the more advanced traditional media for creation of a loyal audience and design of new business models in the digital environment.⁶

We are residing in a brand-new information age. It is clear that knowledge has a huge impact on every facet of society's existence in the global community. Humanity now has the ability to stay informed about events happening throughout the globe. As a result of everything mentioned above, traditional media has evolved into an international web. Individual information websites followed the initial appearance of electronic copies of conventional printed periodicals.

The advent of digital television allowed for the organisation of Internet radio and Internet broadcasting, and the development of television and radio broadcasting also achieved a qualitatively new level. For instance, "real-time" programmes on events happening concurrently throughout the programme are now aired on the Internet. These broadcasts can duplicate the broadcasting of traditional television, and can be re-releases or original Internet programs. According to K.A. Shergova "During the live broadcast, the user has the opportunity in real time to interact with the producer of the broadcast; he can receive additional information from him, direct questions to the

⁶ Anna Kachkaeva. "Digital media and the Internet market: Audiences, multimedia content and business models". From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012 <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/8/3/102312>

program guests, take part in interactive surveys, and influence the further outcome of the program.”⁷

Numerous websites that offer videos, like YouTube, as well as social networking sites like Facebook, Twitter, and others, have become extremely popular. Undoubtedly, each of these elements has shaped the growth of free speech and thought diversity, which are the cornerstones of democracy. According to the research of F.Mahmudova, social media mediatext frequently makes emotional and compelling claims in an effort to grab users' attention and change their views and actions. Strong emotional reactions to emotionally charged content can influence how people absorb and retain information. Persuasive strategies like social proof, storytelling, and framing can influence how people think and make decisions.⁸

It must be said that at the present time, a great role is ascribed to the Internet in the future development of the media sphere in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has chosen the path of active development of Internet technologies. Today, the number of Internet users in Uzbekistan exceeds nine million. The Program for Further Adoption of ICT Development is being implemented. Almost all the traditional media already have their sites on the Internet. In addition, about 200 sites are registered as separate Internet media. Powerful modern data processing centers have been created in Uzbekistan, enabling users, including the media, to store and process large volumes of data. A total of more than 750,000 users visit domestic media sites each month.⁹

Global communication has grown as new mediums, including the Internet, have become more popular. Thanks to the Internet, people may now express themselves through user-generated media such as blogs, websites, images, and other media. As the Internet has developed, operations in the fields of education, business, administration, development, and other fields have all become increasingly global. The culture of the

⁷ K.A. Shergova. Documentary telefilms and Internet. Academy of media industry. Electronic and print media newsletter. Newsletter 12.

⁸ Fotima Maxmudova. "Cognition of mediatext in social media". *Medialingvistika, lingvodidaktika va madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya: nazariya va amaliyot – 2023*, pp.72-76

⁹ Firdavs Abdukhalikov. Social and new media in Central Asia. From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012

Internet has advanced humankind and aided in its general growth. For people from all areas of life, internet technology has also enhanced information availability and utility.

The Internet has created its own kind, fourth kind of journalism: online journalism - which differs in its characteristics from traditional types of journalism (Deuze, 1999). Online journalism can be functionally differentiated from other kinds of journalism by using its technological component as a determining factor in terms of (operational) definition. The relevance of defining online journalism as such and its portée for the profession as a whole can be summarised quoting Peter Dahlgren's observation that: "Journalism is carried out in specific institutional circumstances, within concrete organisational settings and under particular technological conditions. The advent of cyberspace will inevitably impact on the factors which shape how journalism gets done - and may well even colour how we define what journalism is".¹⁰

In conclusion, we can say that many academics in subjects such as education, psychology, and sociology have investigated the impact of the Internet on people and society, as well as the benefits and drawbacks of utilising it. The Internet has a favourable and harmful impact on children, teenagers, women, and other members of society in modern civilization. According to the most recent Internet survey, approximately 900 million people were online worldwide. According to the findings, almost all educational institutions around the world, regardless of level, geography, or poverty concentration, have Internet connection. Because Internet use among users is rapidly increasing, experts need to understand the influence of the Internet as a medium of communication in modern society. And as Mark Deuz mentioned in his research, when one looks closely at the news websites of the "traditional" media nowadays, one notices that most of them resemble print newspaper front pages in a very similar way. Recently, a Web designer colleague expressed her opinion that online news sites are all attempting, in her opinion, a desperate attempt to appear "serious," even going so far as to imply that users do not typically "read" or trust online news sources. Our

¹⁰ Dahlgren, P. (1996). Media logic in cyberspace: repositioning journalism and its publics. *Javnost/The Public* 3:3, pp.59-72.

research does indicate that the journalists employed by various websites have distinct perspectives regarding their readers, as well as their place and contribution to society. According to other research, people don't seem to mind reading or having any credibility issues with internet news—they just read and "believe" differently. Starting point for considering any 'new' ejournalism should therefore be its challenge to our core assumptions about the mass media, society and its journalisms.¹¹

References:

1. Javier Díaz Noci. "A history of journalism on the internet: A state of the art and some methodological trends". *Revista internacional de Historia de la Comunicación*, N°1, Vol.1, año 2013, PP. 253-272
2. Abhram, William. "The Internet as a Modern-day Communication Medium." *J Mass Communicate Journalism* 12 (2022): 453.
3. Anna Kachkaeva. "Digital media and the Internet market: Audiences, multimedia content and business models". *From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012* <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/8/3/102312>
4. Anna Kachkaeva. "Digital media and the Internet market: Audiences, multimedia content and business models". *From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012* <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/8/3/102312>
5. Mark Deuze. "Understanding the impact of the Internet: On new media professionalism, mindsets and buzzwords" (January, 2001). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254750080>
6. Anna Kachkaeva. "Digital media and the Internet market: Audiences, multimedia content and business models". *From traditional to online media: Best*

¹¹ Mark Deuze. "Understanding the impact of the Internet: On new media professionalism, mindsets and buzzwords" (January, 2001). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254750080>

practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012 <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/8/3/102312>

7. K.A. Shergova. Documentary telefilms and Internet. Academy of media industry. Electronic and print media newsletter. Newsletter 12.

8. Fotima Maxmudova. “Cognition of mediatext in social media”. Medialingvistika, lingvodidaktika va madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya: nazariya va amaliyot – 2023, pp.72-76

9.Firdavs Abdukhalikov. Social and new media in Central Asia. From traditional to online media: Best practices and perspectives 14th Central Asia Media Conference Ashgabat, Turkmenistan 5-6 July 2012

10. Dahlgren, P. (1996). Media logic in cyberspace: repositioning journalism and its publics. *Javnost/The Public* 3:3, pp.59-72.

11.Mark Deuze. “Understanding the impact of the Internet: On new media professionalism, mindsets and buzzwords” (January, 2001). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254750080>